

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

The property market, a base of global economies, has traditionally relied heavily on human expertise and complex processes. However, recent advancements in technology, particularly in Artificial Intelligence, are reshaping the market by offering new opportunities for efficiency, innovation, and value creation (Li & Du, 2020). Artificial Intelligence, which involves machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision, is changing how property-related tasks are performed, leveraging advanced algorithms and data analytics to automate processes and optimise decision-making (Chen 2019).

Machine Learning algorithms, a subset of artificial intelligence enable computers to learn from data and make predictions or decisions without any applied programming. In real estate, Machine learning algorithms are used for various applications, including property valuation, demand forecasting, and risk assessment, thus empowering players in the market with valuable insights (Li & Du, 2020). Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques enable machines to understand and interpret human language, facilitating tasks such as sentiment analysis of property listings and personalised customer interactions, thereby enhancing the overall client experience (Bennett et al., 2019).

Computer vision technologies enable machines to interpret and analyse visual information, such as images and videos. In real estate, computer vision is employed for tasks such as property image recognition, virtual property tours, and automated property condition assessments, thereby streamlining processes and reducing manual effort (Chen., 2019). Despite the promising potential of artificial intelligence in real estate, its widespread adoption faces challenges such as data privacy concerns, technological barriers, and regulatory constraints, necessitating a comprehensive assessment of its viability and implications in specific contexts (Li & Du, 2020).

Thus, this study aims to evaluate the feasibility and potential impact of Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market. By examining factors such as data availability, technological infrastructure, regulatory environment, and stakeholder perspectives, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into the opportunities and challenges associated with artificial intelligence adoption in real estate within the Akure context. Through a systematic analysis, this study aims to inform policymakers, industry practitioners, and other stakeholders about the transformative potential of artificial intelligence in shaping the future of the Akure property market and beyond.

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1.2. Statement of the Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligence in the property industry presents both opportunities and challenges, particularly in emerging markets such as the Akure property market. Despite the potential benefits of artificial intelligence implementation, the views of Estate Surveyors and Valuers, towards this new technology remain largely unknown. Understanding this is essential for informing policy decisions and shaping the future of artificial intelligence adoption in the Akure property market (Li & Du, 2020; Bennett, 2019).

The successful implementation of artificial intelligence in the Akure property market depends on identifying and addressing the key factors influencing its adoption. These factors involve a wide range of considerations, including technological readiness, data availability, regulatory frameworks, and stakeholder engagement. A board analysis of these factors is essential for knowing the effective strategies for utilising the potential of artificial intelligence in addressing real estate challenges and enhancing market efficiency (Chen, 2019).

Adopting Artificial Intelligence in the Akure property market is not without its barriers. Various barriers, such as data privacy concerns, skills gaps, and cultural resistance, may impede the integration of artificial intelligence technologies. Identifying and understanding these barriers is essential for understanding the strategies and ensuring a successful implementation of artificial intelligence solutions in the study area (Li & Du, 2020; Bennett, 2019).

In addressing these problems, it is necessary to identify the most suitable artificial intelligence tools and methodologies for effectively addressing real estate challenges in the Akure property market. By introducing advanced artificial intelligence technologies such as machine learning, natural language processing, and computer vision. Estate surveyors and valuers can develop innovative solutions tailored to the required and dynamic needs of the Akure property market, which will unlock new opportunities for growth and development (Chen, 2019).

1.3. Research Questions

1. What are the perceptions of ESV towards Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market?
2. What are the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area?
3. What are the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area?
4. What are the suitable Artificial Intelligence tools for addressing real estate challenges in the study area?

1.4.0. Aim and Objectives of Study

1.4.1. The aim of this study

Given the background above, provided in the statement of the problem and reheard question this research aims to explore the potentiation of artificial intelligence Technology and its impact on the Nigerian real estate market with a clear view in improving the process of transacting in the market, by using Akure as a case study.

1.4.2. Objectives of the study

- i. Examine the perceptions of ESV towards Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market;
- ii. Assess the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area;
- iii. Identify the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area;
- iv. Examine the suitable Artificial Intelligence technology for addressing real estate challenges in the study area.

1.5. Justification of study

The justification of this study depends on its potential to contribute to the advancement of the property market in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, through the strategic implementation of Artificial Intelligence technologies. As an emerging market, the Akure property market is positioned for growth and development, presenting opportunities and challenges for stakeholders. By exploring the potential of this technology for Estate Surveyors and Values, this study seeks to provide valuable insights that can inform decision-making processes and shape the future of the Akure property market (Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020).

The study will investigate the factors influencing the adoption of artificial intelligence in the Akure property market. Understanding these factors is essential for knowing the strategies and interventions aimed at overcoming the barriers to implementation and maximising the potential benefits of artificial intelligence technologies. By identifying key drivers and inhibitors of the adoption, stakeholders can make informed decisions regarding investment, policy development, and capacity-building initiatives; this will expedite the innovation and sustainable growth of the property market (Adeloye & Okedeji, 2021).

Moreover, this study is relevant to Nigeria's broader efforts to adopt digital transformation and utilise the potential of emerging technologies for economic development. With the government's initiatives such as the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy and the Nigeria National Artificial Intelligence Roadmap, there is a growing

campaign to introduce artificial intelligence to drive innovation, enhance productivity, and improve service delivery across various markets, including property market (Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020). By aligning with these national priorities and focusing on the Akure property market, this study contributes to the realisation of Nigeria's vision of becoming a leading digital economy in Africa.

1.6. The Study Scope

This study focuses mainly on the perceptions, factors, and barriers influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the Akure property market, Ondo State, Nigeria. The scope of the study involves Estate Surveyors and Valuers operating within the Akure property market, as their insights and perspectives are necessary to understand the dynamics of the technology in the property market. By conducting surveys, interviews, and discussions with relevant stakeholders, including professionals, buyers, and sellers, this study aims to capture a comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges associated with the implementation in the Akure property market (Adesina et al., 2020).

Also, the scope of the study extends to the identification and evaluation of artificial intelligence tools and methodologies for addressing property challenges specific to the Akure market. Accessing the insights from existing literature, case studies, and expert consultations, this study seeks to recommend the technology solutions narrowed to the advancement of the Akure property market. By providing practical guidance and recommendations, this research aims to facilitate decision-making processes and stimulate innovation in the market, contributing to the sustainable development of Akure and Nigeria's broader economic objectives (Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020).

1.7. Study Area

The study area is the city of Akure, which is the capital of Ondo State, Nigeria. Ondo State, located in the southwestern region of Nigeria, is a rapidly growing urban center characterised by its real estate market and diverse

economic activities. As the capital city of the state, Akure attracts notable investment in residential, commercial, and industrial properties, driving demand for real estate services and infrastructure development (Olatunji ., 2019).

The Akure property market is influenced by various socio-economic factors, including population growth, urbanisation, infrastructure development, and government policies. The city's location, favourable climate, tertiary institutions, and proximity to major road networks contribute to its attractiveness as a residential and commercial destination. However, the property market in Akure is also affected by challenges such as land use conflicts, inadequate infrastructure, and informal land tenure systems, which impact property valuation, investment decisions, and market structure (Adewale, 2018). By focusing on the Akure property market, this research aims to provide insights into the opportunities and challenges associated with the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the Nigerian property market.

Explanation of Terms

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence refers to the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems. These processes include learning, reasoning, problem-solving, perception, and language understanding. It enables machines to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as understanding natural language, recognizing patterns in data, making decisions, and learning from experience.

Machine Learning

Machine Learning is a subset of Artificial Intelligence that focuses on the development of algorithms and models that allow computers to learn from data and make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed. In essence, machine learning algorithms enable computers

to identify patterns and relationships within large datasets, adapt and improve over time-based on new data, and make informed decisions or predictions.

Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Processing is a branch of Artificial Intelligence that focuses on enabling computers to understand, interpret, and generate human language in a manner that is both meaningful and contextually relevant. NLP algorithms are used to analyse and process natural language data, including text and speech, to perform tasks such as sentiment analysis, language translation, information extraction, and question-answering.

Computer Vision

Computer Vision is a field of Artificial Intelligence that enables computers to interpret and understand visual information from the real world, such as images and videos. Computer vision algorithms are used to extract meaningful insights from visual data, including object recognition, scene understanding, image segmentation, and motion detection. Applications of computer vision range from autonomous vehicles and medical imaging to facial recognition and augmented reality.

Algorithms

Algorithms are step-by-step procedures or sets of rules that specify how to solve a particular problem or perform a specific task. In the context of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, algorithms are mathematical formulas or processes that enable computers to learn from

data, make predictions, or perform other tasks. Examples of algorithms include decision trees, neural networks, support vector machines, and clustering algorithms.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0. Introduction

This literature review discusses strategic innovation and the cycle of technologies in the Nigerian real estate market, with a focus on assessing the viability of implementing artificial intelligence in the Akure property market. The review explores the conceptual framework of Artificial intelligence which includes an overview, characteristics, and regulatory framework in Nigeria. It discusses the Akure Property Market, current practices, and the challenges in the market. The review also points out the theoretical framework, perceived benefits, challenges, readiness, and adoption of artificial intelligence in the market. This will provide a comprehensive understanding of how artificial intelligence can remodel the Akure real estate market, judging from best practices across the world.

2.1 Strategic Innovation and the Cycle of Technologies in the Nigerian Real Estate Market.

Strategic innovation in the Nigerian real estate market is influenced by the introduction of Artificial Intelligence and other emerging technologies. These innovations are remodeling the landscape by introducing new methods for property management, valuation, and transaction processes. The application of artificial intelligence in real estate offers the potential to increase performance, cut costs, and improve decision-making. A very good example is the use of algorithms to analyze a large pool of data to identify market trends, predict property values, and appraise investment risks, this will provide valuable insights that have not been known. (Adesina, 2020).

Artificial Intelligence in the Nigerian real estate market is part of a broader cycle of technological innovation that includes other emerging technologies such as blockchain, the Internet of Things, and augmented reality. Blockchain technology, for example, is being used because of its potential to provide secure and transparent property transactions. This technology can help reduce fraud and increase trust by

creating immutable records of property ownership and transactions (Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020). Similarly, IoT devices can be used to enhance property management by monitoring building systems and conditions in real-time, leading to more performance maintenance and energy management.

The cycle of technological adoption in the Nigerian real estate market can be assessed through the Gartner Hype Cycle, which describes the phases of a technology's maturity and adoption. Initially, new technologies experience a peak of inflated expectations, followed by a trough of despondency as early implementations face challenges. As technologies mature, they reach a slope of

Enlightenment, where more practical applications are developed, leads to a plateau in productivity. Artificial Intelligence and other emerging technologies in the Nigerian real estate market are currently transitioning from early adoption phases to more widespread and practical applications, as stakeholders recognize their potential to drive innovation and productivity (Gartner, 2020).

However, the integration of these technologies also presents challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize their benefits. Issues such as data privacy, regulatory compliance, and the need for technical expertise are notable barriers to adoption. Additionally, there is a need for investment in infrastructure and training to support the deployment of Artificial Intelligence and other technologies in the real estate market. Collaborative efforts between government, industry stakeholders, and technology providers are essential to create an enabling environment for innovation and to address these challenges effectively (Adesina . 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020).

2.2 Conceptual Framework of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, enabling them to perform tasks that typically require human cognition. The concept of artificial intelligence encompasses

a broad range of techniques and approaches aimed at enabling computers to perceive, reason, learn, and act independently in complex environments. One of the fundamental goals of artificial intelligence is to develop systems that can replicate human-like intelligence, enabling machines to understand natural language, recognize patterns, solve problems, and make decisions independently with human effort (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

These systems depend on various methodologies and techniques to emulate human intelligence, including machine learning, neural networks, natural language processing, computer vision, and expert systems. Machine learning, in particular, plays a central role in artificial intelligence by allowing machines to learn from data and improve their performance over time without being programmed. Neural networks, influenced by the structure of the human brain, are computational models capable of learning complex patterns and relationships within data, enabling artificial Intelligence systems to recognize objects, understand speech, and generate human-like responses (Goodfellow, 2016).

The concept of Artificial Intelligence has changed notably since its invention, with rapid advancements in computing power, data availability, and algorithmic innovation driving its progress. Today, these technologies are spread across various industries, including healthcare, finance, transportation, and real estate, where they are used to automate routine tasks, optimize processes, and unlock new insights from data. As Artificial intelligence continues to advance, it holds the potential to reset society, transform economies, and reshape the way we live and work (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

2.2.1. An Overview of Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria

Artificial Intelligence is gaining traction in Nigeria, with increasing recognition of its transformative potential across various industries of the economy. In recent years, Nigeria has witnessed a growing

interest in technology research, development, and application, fueled by advancements, an exponential startup ecosystem, and government initiatives aimed at enabling digital innovation (Adeloye & Okedeji, 2021). The Nigerian government's National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy point to the importance of artificial intelligence in driving economic growth, promoting innovation, and addressing societal challenges, positioning artificial intelligence as a key enabler of Nigeria's digital transformation agenda (Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020).

There is an increasing ecosystem of artificial intelligence startups, research institutions, and initiatives aimed at harnessing artificial intelligence to address local challenges and drive socio-economic development. Nigerian entrepreneurs and innovators are leveraging these technologies to develop solutions in areas such as healthcare, agriculture, finance, and education, with the potential to transform service delivery, enhance productivity, and improve livelihoods (Adeloye & Okedeji, 2021). However, challenges such as data privacy concerns, skills gaps, and infrastructure limitations pose serious problems to the widespread adoption and scalability of artificial Intelligence solutions in Nigeria, highlighting the need for concerted efforts by stakeholders to overcome these barriers and unlock the full potential of artificial Intelligence for Nigeria's development (Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020).

On April 22, 2024. The Federal Ministry of Communications, Innovation, and Digital Economy recently organized a workshop to co-create Nigeria's National Artificial Intelligence Strategy. Aligned with the administration's agenda of accelerating diversification through industrialization and digitization, the strategy employs a human-centered design (HCD) approach to address both national and global needs. The four-day workshop brought together key stakeholders from the public and private sectors, along with global experts, to deliberate on artificial Intelligence's transformative potential. Minister Dr. Bosun Tijani emphasized participants' collective responsibility in leveraging artificial intelligence for societal betterment, stressing inclusivity and unity in shaping its trajectory. Permanent Secretary Engr. Faruk

Yabo highlighted Artificial Intelligence potential across various markets and highlighted the importance of a culturally sensitive and implementable strategy. Director-General Mallam Kashifu Abdullahi emphasized the role of Artificial Intelligence in driving societal change and the workshop's collaborative nature in developing an inclusive strategy. Breakout sessions focused on contextualizing artificial Intelligence strategy and goal-setting, with syndicates presenting strategic initiatives. The event concluded with optimism about the development of a robust National Artificial Intelligence Strategy, positioning Nigeria as a leader in artificial Intelligence adoption and fostering socioeconomic progress (Nkechi, 2024).

2.2.2. Characteristics of Artificial Intelligence

Adaptability: One of the key characteristics of Artificial Intelligence is adaptability, which refers to the ability of artificial intelligence systems to learn from new data and experiences and adjust their behavior accordingly. Artificial Intelligence algorithms are designed to adapt and improve over time through a process known as machine learning, enabling them to continually refine their performance and effectiveness (Russell & Norvig, 2021). This adaptability allows artificial Intelligence systems to address complex and evolving challenges across various domains, from healthcare and finance to transportation and cyber security.

Autonomy: Autonomy is another important characteristic of Artificial Intelligence, referring to the ability of artificial Intelligence systems to perform tasks and make decisions independently without human intervention. Autonomous artificial Intelligence systems are capable of analyzing data, generating insights, and taking actions based on predefined objectives or criteria, without the need for constant human oversight (Russell & Norvig, 2021). This autonomy enables artificial

Intelligence systems operate in real-time, adapt to changing environments, and execute tasks diligently, thereby enhancing productivity and scalability in diverse applications.

Interpretability: Interpretability is the capacity of artificial Intelligence systems to explain their decisions, predictions, or recommendations in a human-understandable manner. Transparent artificial Intelligence models enable users to understand the underlying rationale behind artificial intelligence-generated outputs, facilitating trust, accountability, and regulatory compliance (Molnar, 2021). Interpretability is particularly crucial in high-stakes domains such as healthcare, finance, and criminal justice, where artificial Intelligence decisions can have an important impact on individuals and society. By providing interpretable outputs, artificial Intelligence systems empower users to validate model outputs, identify biases or errors, and make informed decisions based on reliable information.

Scalability: Scalability refers to the ability of artificial Intelligence systems to handle increasing volumes of data, computational tasks, and users without compromising performance or ability. Scalable artificial Intelligence architectures and algorithms enable organizations to deploy artificial Intelligence solutions across large-scale applications, serving diverse user needs and accommodating growing data volumes (Russell & Norvig, 2021). Scalability is essential for ensuring the practical utility and viability of artificial Intelligence systems in real-world settings, where demands for processing power, storage capacity, and responsiveness can vary dynamically.

Robustness: Robustness is the capability of Artificial Intelligence systems to maintain performance and reliability in the face of unforeseen challenges, adversarial inputs, or changing conditions. Robust artificial Intelligence algorithms exhibit resilience to noise, uncertainty, and perturbations, ensuring consistent performance across diverse environments and scenarios (Russell & Norvig, 2021). Robustness is critical for deploying Artificial Intelligence systems in safety-critical applications such as autonomous

vehicles, medical diagnosis, and industrial automation, where errors or failures can have severe consequences.

2.2.3. Regulatory Framework of Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria

Artificial Intelligence technologies hold immense potential for various industries in Nigeria, including real estate. However, the absence of a comprehensive regulatory framework poses challenges in ensuring responsible artificial intelligence deployment and safeguarding against potential risks. Establishing a regulatory framework for artificial intelligence in Nigeria is crucial to aid innovation, protect consumer rights, and mitigate ethical and societal concerns.

Legislative and Policy Development

Nigeria is recently shaping its legislative and policy environment to regulate Artificial Intelligence and utilize its benefits for economic diversification and societal advancement. The cornerstone of this effort is the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS), which aims to leverage digital technologies, including Artificial Intelligence, to drive economic growth. The Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy, has been instrumental in this initiative. NITDA, tasked with developing the National Artificial Intelligence Policy (NAIP), aims to provide a comprehensive framework that addresses the development, deployment, and adoption of Artificial Intelligence technologies in Nigeria. This policy is designed to maximize Artificial Intelligence benefits while mitigating risks, reflecting a proactive approach to integrating Artificial Intelligence into Nigeria's economic and social fabric.

The legislative framework for Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria also emphasizes the need for robust data protection and ethical standards. Current data protection regulations, such as the Nigeria Data Protection

Regulation (NDPR), provide a foundation, but there is a recognized need for more specific laws to address the unique challenges posed by Artificial Intelligence. The National Assembly has been urged to develop comprehensive data privacy laws that offer effective safeguards against the misuse of personal data by Artificial Intelligence systems. Moreover, the government is focusing on creating ethical guidelines to ensure Artificial Intelligence systems operate transparently and accountably, preventing biases and protecting human rights. This legislative effort is part of a broader strategy to align Nigeria's Artificial Intelligence policies with global best practices and to foster a regulatory environment that supports innovation while safeguarding public interests (OAL Law).

Data Protection and Privacy:

Data protection and privacy are critical components of Nigeria's Artificial Intelligence regulatory framework, emphasized by the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR). This regulation provides a robust framework to ensure the privacy and security of personal data handled by Artificial Intelligence systems. The NDPR mandates that organizations processing personal data implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect against data breaches and unauthorized access. These measures include encryption, access controls, and regular security audits to ensure compliance. The regulation aims to protect individuals' data rights, mitigate risks associated with Artificial Intelligence data processing, and foster trust in Artificial Intelligence technologies.

In addition to the NDPR, there is an ongoing push for more comprehensive data protection laws tailored specifically to the unique challenges posed by Artificial Intelligence. Legislators and stakeholders advocate for policies that provide effective legal safeguards for data collection and automated decision-making processes. Such laws would address concerns about data misuse, algorithmic bias, and the transparency of Artificial Intelligence systems. By ensuring that Artificial Intelligence applications

comply with stringent data protection standards, Nigeria aims to mitigate the risks of data exploitation and uphold the principles of privacy and human dignity in the digital age (OAL Law) (Further Africa).

Ethical Standards:

Ethical standards in Nigeria's Artificial Intelligence regulation framework are designed to ensure that Artificial Intelligence systems operate transparently, fairly, and accountably, safeguarding human rights and democratic values. The National Artificial Intelligence Policy (NAIP) under development by the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) emphasizes these ethical considerations. This policy aims to mitigate biases in Artificial Intelligence algorithms, which have shown tendencies to discriminate based on race and other factors. Such biases can lead to significant injustices, as seen in the case of facial recognition systems erroneously identifying individuals, which disproportionately affects marginalized groups (OAL Law).

Moreover, the Nigerian approach to Artificial Intelligence ethics stresses the importance of transparency in Artificial Intelligence decision-making processes. This is critical in preventing the "black box effect," where Artificial Intelligence systems produce outcomes that are not easily understandable or explainable. Ensuring transparency is essential for maintaining public trust and enabling stakeholders to challenge and seek redress for unjust decisions. These ethical guidelines are designed to align Artificial Intelligence development with fundamental principles of fairness

and justice, as well as to support Nigeria's broader goals of leveraging Artificial Intelligence for economic and social benefits while protecting individual rights (OAL Law).

Intellectual Property Rights:

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are pivotal in Nigeria's Artificial Intelligence regulatory framework, ensuring that Artificial Intelligence innovations are adequately protected and incentivized. Companies

engaged in Artificial Intelligence development are encouraged to secure their trade secrets through Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) with employees, contractors, and any other parties who may access sensitive information. This approach helps prevent the unauthorized use or dissemination of proprietary Artificial Intelligence technologies. Moreover, Nigerian regulations mandate that technology agreements involving foreign entities must be registered with the National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP). This registration facilitates access to the official foreign exchange market for paying license fees, thus supporting legal compliance and fostering an environment conducive to technological advancement and innovation

Additionally, the Nigerian intellectual property framework necessitates that technological inventions, including Artificial Intelligence algorithms and applications, meet specific eligibility criteria before they can be registered as patents or trademarks. This ensures that only qualified innovations receive protection, thereby encouraging genuine innovation and creativity within the Artificial Intelligence sector. The comprehensive guidelines provided by NOTAP and other regulatory bodies ensure that intellectual property rights are preserved, thereby promoting a robust ecosystem for Artificial Intelligence research and development. Protecting intellectual property is not only about securing the economic interests of innovators but also about maintaining Nigeria's competitive edge in the global Artificial Intelligence market.

Research and developments:

Research and development in Artificial Intelligence is a pivotal aspect of Nigeria's strategy to harness the potential of emerging technologies. The establishment of the National Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (NCAIR) by the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) exemplifies the country's commitment to advancing Artificial Intelligence research. This center facilitates research activities and innovation in Artificial Intelligence and robotics, aiming to develop

technologies that align with national interests and contribute to economic growth. Additionally, collaborations with universities and research institutions are actively encouraged to foster an ecosystem of innovation and technological advancement.

Furthermore, the Nigerian government recognizes the importance of supporting R&D through strategic investments and policy initiatives. The National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) underscores the role of Artificial Intelligence in driving economic diversification and sustainable development. By investing in basic and applied Artificial Intelligence research, as well as training specialists in Artificial Intelligence technologies, the government aims to build a robust foundation for the digital economy. These efforts are designed to not only enhance technological capabilities but also address socio-economic challenges through innovative Artificial Intelligence solutions.

Capacity Building:

Capacity building is a critical component of Nigeria's regulatory framework for Artificial Intelligence, focusing on developing the necessary skills and infrastructure to support Artificial Intelligence innovation and implementation. The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) plays a pivotal role in this effort, spearheading initiatives such as the establishment of the National Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (NCAIR). This center aims to foster research and development in Artificial Intelligence, facilitating collaborations between academic institutions, industry stakeholders, and government bodies. Additionally, the Nigerian government emphasizes the importance of training specialists in Artificial Intelligence technologies and enhancing the digital infrastructure to create a robust ecosystem for Artificial Intelligence growth.

The government's approach to capacity building includes comprehensive education and training programs designed to equip individuals with the skills needed to drive Artificial Intelligence advancements. These programs are crucial for creating a workforce capable of leveraging Artificial

Intelligence technologies to address local challenges and contribute to economic development. By investing in human capital and digital infrastructure, Nigeria aims to harness the full potential of Artificial Intelligence, ensuring that the country remains competitive in the global Artificial Intelligence landscape. This strategy is aligned with the broader objectives of the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS), which seeks to diversify the Nigerian economy through the strategic use of digital technologies

Regulatory Bodies:

In Nigeria, several regulatory bodies play pivotal roles in overseeing the development, implementation, and compliance of artificial intelligence technologies. The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) is at the forefront, tasked with developing standards, guidelines, and frameworks essential for the IT sector, including artificial intelligence. Established under the NITDA Act 2007, this agency also oversees the National Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Robotics (NCAIR), which promotes Artificial Intelligence research and innovation. NITDA's responsibilities extend to the creation of the National Artificial Intelligence Policy (NAIP), aimed at maximizing artificial intelligence benefits while mitigating associated risks.

Other regulatory bodies also contribute significantly to the artificial intelligence regulatory landscape. For instance, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) requires companies providing artificial intelligence-powered financial services to obtain relevant financial licenses, ensuring these services adhere to sector-specific regulations. Similarly, the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) mandates the registration of artificial intelligence-powered stock trading services. Furthermore, the National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP) facilitates the registration of technology transfer agreements, which is crucial for foreign technology collaborations and accessing the official foreign exchange market. These regulatory measures ensure that artificial intelligence innovations are integrated into Nigeria's economic framework responsibly and effectively.

Collaboration and International Standards:

Collaboration with international organizations and adherence to global artificial intelligence standards are essential for harmonizing regulatory frameworks and fostering interoperability. Nigeria should actively participate in international forums such as the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the OECD to exchange best practices, leverage expertise, and contribute to the development of global artificial intelligence governance frameworks (ITU, 2023).

2.3. An Overview of the Akure Property Market

The property market in Akure metropolis, the capital city of Ondo State in southwestern Nigeria, is known to be a mix of traditional practices and emerging challenges. Property transactions in the Akure metropolis are usually conducted through conventional methods, involving face-to-face negotiations, physical property inspections, and manual paperwork, with real estate agents and the Ministry of Lands and Housing playing key roles in facilitating these processes (Akinyemi, 2018). Property valuation relies heavily on manual and traditional approaches, where estate surveyors use comparable sales data to estimate property values, a method that can be time-consuming and lacks precision in most cases (Oluwaseun & Babajide, 2020). The procedural process of land registration and documentation involves different departments in the Ondo State Ministry of Lands and Housing, resulting in delays and ineffectiveness (Akinwunmi, 2019). Property management in the metropolis is handled by property agents, landlords, or caretakers, relying on manual practices that can lead to inconsistencies and disputes (Olajide, 2021). Furthermore, the market faces challenges such as limited transparency, inadequate technological adoption, and a shortage of professionals skilled in ever-developing real estate practices, which would affect the market's growth and productivity (Oluwaseun & Babajide, 2020).

2.3.1 Current Practices in the Akure Metropolis Property Market

Current Practices in the Akure Metropolis Property Market. The capital city of Ondo State is known for several traditional practices that shape its operations. These practices include property transactions, property valuation, land registration and documentation, and property management.

Property Transactions

In Akure, property transactions mostly follow traditional methods. These methods involve face-to-face negotiations between buyers and sellers, physical property inspections, and manual completion of paperwork. Real estate agents or the land ministry and buyers are the players, leveraging personal networks and local knowledge to facilitate transactions. Despite this approach, it often results in slower transaction times and higher costs due to the manual nature of the processes (Akinyemi, 2018). The dependence on physical inspections and manual documentation can also introduce errors and delays, which affect the overall performance of property transactions.

Property Valuation

The valuation of properties in Akure is primarily conducted using manual methods. Estate surveyors and values employ the comparable sales approach, where they assess property values by comparing them with recent sales of similar properties in the vicinity. This method, while practical, is time-consuming and can lack precision, especially in the absence of comprehensive and up-to-date market data (Oluwaseun & Babajide, 2020). The reliance on manual processes and limited access to robust data sources can result in valuation discrepancies, which impact market transparency and investor confidence.

Land Registration and Documentation

The process of land registration and obtaining property documentation in Akure and Ondo state generally involves different offices in the state land and housing ministry, making it a cumbersome and lengthy

ordeal. This process includes verifying land ownership, obtaining necessary permits, and ensuring compliance with local regulations. The involvement of various administrative layers and the need for numerous physical documents can create unnecessary delays, discouraging investment and complicating property transactions (Akinwunmi, 2019). These administrative barriers often lead to prolonged processing times and can deter potential investors due to the uncertainty and complexity involved.

Property Management

Property management in Akure is generally handled by individual landlords or small property management firms. These managers oversee tenant relations, maintenance, and rent collection manually. This traditional management style can lead to inconsistencies and disorganization, as it heavily relies on the personal efforts and discretion of the landlords or managers (Olajide, 2021). Without standardized processes or technological support, issues such as delayed maintenance, rent arrears, and tenant disputes are more common. This can affect the overall tenant experience and the profitability of rental properties.

2.3.2 Challenges in the Akure Metropolis Property Market

Despite the growth and development observed in Akure's property market, several challenges persist due to the dependence on traditional practices. These challenges affect performance, transparency, and overall market development. Below are the common challenges identified in the current practices of the Akure metropolis property market:

Inaccurate Valuation Methods

One of the main challenges in the Akure property market is the dependence on manual valuation methods. Estate surveyors and valuers mostly use the comparable sales approach, which involves comparing the property in question with recent sales of similar properties in the area. This method can be time-

consuming and often lacks precision, especially without access to comprehensive and up-to-date market data. As a result, property valuations can be inconsistent and inaccurate, affecting market transparency and investor confidence (Oluwaseun & Babajide, 2020). The lack of automated valuation models (AVMs) and other advanced tools further worsens this issue, leading to potential undervaluation or overvaluation of properties.

Complicated Process

The process of land registration and obtaining property documentation in Akure is known to have irrelevant bureaucratic inefficiencies. Different land-related offices in the Ministry are involved, and the process includes verifying land ownership, obtaining necessary permits, and ensuring compliance with local regulations. This process is often slow and prone to delays due to the need for numerous approvals and physical documents. These processes can discourage investment and complicate property transactions, leading to prolonged processing times and increased transaction costs (Akinwunmi, 2019). Also, the lack of a centralized digital system for land records further complicates the process, making it challenging to verify property titles and ownership quickly.

Lack of Transparency

Transparency is a critical issue in the Akure property market. Limited access to reliable market data and the prevalence of informal transactions make it difficult for buyers and sellers to make informed decisions. The customary land ownership of land in the metropolis has never given a chance for transparency. The absence of a centralized database for property listings, transaction histories, and market trends contributes to this lack of transparency. This opacity can lead to disputes and reduce market organization, as buyers and sellers cannot accurately assess market conditions or property values (Oluwaseun & Babajide, 2020). Furthermore, the lack of standardized processes and regulatory policy

allows for unethical practices, such as fraud, omo-oniles, and misrepresentation, which occur more frequently.

Poor Technological Adoption

The adoption of advanced technologies, including artificial intelligence, is limited in the Akure property market. Most real estate practices remain manual and traditional, missing out on the effectiveness and enhancements that technology can offer. For example, artificial intelligence-driven tools for property valuation, transaction management, and market analysis can improve accuracy and speed. However, the lack of technological infrastructure and expertise means that these tools are not widely used, resulting in slower transactions and less effective market operations (Olajide, 2021). This technological gap not only affects operational competence but also limits the market's ability to attract and retain investors who expect modern, tech-driven solutions.

Limited Professional Expertise

There is a notable shortage of professionals with expertise in modern real estate practices and technologies in Akure. This skills gap limits the market's ability to innovate and adopt new tools that can enhance property management, valuation, and transaction processes. Without adequate training and education, real estate professionals are less equipped to implement advanced technologies or adapt to new industry standards. This limitation hampers the overall growth and modernization of the market, making it difficult to compete with more advanced real estate markets (Oluwaseun & Babajide, 2020). Enhancing professional expertise through targeted education and training programs is essential to address this challenge.

2.4.1 Theoretical Framework of Implementing Artificial Intelligence in Real Estate

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is one of the most widely used frameworks for understanding technology adoption. Developed by Davis (1989), TAM posits that the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of a technology significantly influence an individual's intention to use it. In the context of real estate, estate professionals are more likely to adopt Artificial Intelligence if they believe that it will make their tasks easier and improve their job performance. For example, Artificial Intelligence can automate repetitive tasks such as data entry and analysis, allowing professionals to focus on more strategic activities. Studies have shown that TAM is a robust predictor of technology adoption across various domains, including real estate (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

Diffusion of Innovations Theory

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory, proposed by Rogers (1962), explains how new technologies spread within a society or organization. The theory identifies five key factors that influence the adoption of an innovation: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, experimental, and fairness. In the real estate sector, the adoption of Artificial Intelligence can be accelerated if it demonstrates clear benefits over traditional methods (relative advantage), aligns with existing workflows (compatibility), is easy to understand and use (complexity), can be tested on a limited basis (experimental), and has visible results (fairness). For instance, Artificial Intelligence -driven property valuation tools that provide more accurate estimates than traditional methods can quickly gain acceptance among estate professionals (Rogers, 2003).

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) integrates elements from several other models, including TAM and the Theory of Planned Behavior. Developed by Venkatesh . (2003), UTAUT identifies four core determinants of technology acceptance: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. In the Nigerian real estate market, performance expectancy might involve the anticipated improvements in property valuation accuracy and market trend predictions due to Artificial Intelligence. Effort expectancy relates to the ease of integrating Artificial Intelligence into existing systems. Social influence encompasses the impact of colleagues and industry leaders endorsing Artificial Intelligence adoption while facilitating conditions referring to the availability of technical infrastructure and support (Venkatesh, 2003).

Task-Technology Fit (TTF)

The Task-Technology Fit (TTF) theory suggests that technology adoption is more likely to succeed when the technology is well-suited to the tasks it is intended to support. Goodhue and Thompson (1995) argue that a high degree of fit between Artificial Intelligence capabilities and real estate tasks will lead to better performance and higher adoption rates. For example, Artificial Intelligence ability to analyze large datasets and generate predictive models aligns well with the tasks of market analysis and property valuation. When estate professionals perceive that Artificial Intelligence tools are specifically designed to enhance their workflow performance, they are more likely to adopt and utilize these technologies (Goodhue & Thompson, 1995).

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)

Social Cognitive Theory, developed by Bandura (1986), emphasises the role of observational learning, social experiences, and reciprocal determinism in behavior change. In the realm of Artificial Intelligence

adoption in real estate, estate professionals may be influenced by the successes and experiences of their peers who have already implemented Artificial Intelligence solutions. Observing the positive outcomes and enhanced performance of colleagues using Artificial Intelligence can motivate others to adopt similar technologies. Additionally, the theory highlights the importance of self-efficacy, or the belief in one's capabilities to learn and implement new technologies, which can be strengthened through training and positive reinforcement (Bandura, 1986).

2.4.2 Perceptions of Artificial Intelligence in Real Estate

The integration of Artificial Intelligence in real estate is accompanied by diverse perceptions among industry stakeholders. These perceptions are shaped by the anticipated benefits Artificial Intelligence can bring to the industry, the perceived challenges associated with its implementation, and the overall readiness of the sector to adopt these technologies.

2.4.2.1 Anticipated Benefits of the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence

Performance and Decision-Making Enhancement:

Many real estate professionals view Artificial Intelligence as a tool that can significantly improve effective decision-making processes. Artificial Intelligence technologies such as predictive analytics and machine learning can analyze large datasets to forecast market trends and property values more accurately, thus aiding in better investment decisions. For instance, predictive analytics can identify market patterns and predict future property prices, helping investors and developers make informed decisions (Raisbeck, 2019).

Automation and Cost Reduction:

Artificial Intelligence -driven automation can handle routine tasks like property management, client inquiries, and transaction processing, thereby reducing operational costs and freeing up human resources for more strategic roles. Automated systems can manage maintenance schedules, process rental payments, and handle customer service queries effectively, which can lead to substantial cost savings and improved operational performance.

Enhanced Client Experience:

Artificial Intelligence can provide personalized services to clients by leveraging data analytics to understand their preferences and behaviors. Artificial Intelligence -powered chatbots and virtual assistants can offer round-the-clock service, answering queries, and providing property recommendations tailored to individual client needs, thus enhancing customer satisfaction and engagement (Levitt, 2018).

Enhanced Due Diligence:

Artificial Intelligence can assist in the due diligence process by quickly and accurately analyzing large volumes of data related to property transactions, such as legal documents, financial records, and market conditions. This helps identify potential risks and ensures compliance with regulatory requirements, thereby reducing the likelihood of costly legal issues (Munir, 2019).

Fraud Detection:

Artificial Intelligence systems can detect patterns indicative of fraudulent activities in real estate transactions. By analyzing transaction histories, buyer/seller profiles, and other relevant data, Artificial

Intelligence can flag suspicious activities for further investigation, helping to protect against fraud and enhance the integrity of real estate markets.

Targeted Marketing:

Artificial Intelligence can analyze consumer data to identify specific target audiences for marketing campaigns. By understanding the preferences and behaviors of potential buyers and renters, real estate professionals can create personalized marketing strategies that are more likely to convert leads into clients (Yousefi & Hammad, 2020).

2.4.1.2 Perceived Challenges of the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in the Real Estate Market

Data Privacy and Security Concerns:

The use of Artificial Intelligence in real estate involves handling large volumes of sensitive data, including the personal and financial information of clients. There are concerns about data breaches and the potential misuse of data. Ensuring robust data protection measures and compliance with data privacy regulations is crucial to mitigate these risks.

Job Displacement:

There is apprehension about the potential loss of jobs due to automation. As Artificial Intelligence takes over routine and administrative tasks, there is a fear that many roles traditionally performed by humans could become redundant, leading to job displacement. This concern is particularly pronounced in segments of the workforce that may not have the skills to transition to new roles created by Artificial Intelligence technology (Kolbe & Wüstemann, 2018). Challenges

High Implementation Costs:

One significant challenge is the high cost of implementing Artificial Intelligence technologies. The initial investment in Artificial Intelligence infrastructure, software, and training can be prohibitive, particularly for smaller real estate firms. These firms may struggle to justify the expenditure without clear, immediate returns on investment (Pogorelc, 2020).

The complexity of Artificial Intelligence Systems:

Implementing Artificial Intelligence technologies often involves complex systems that require specialized knowledge and expertise to develop, maintain, and operate. Real estate firms may face difficulties in understanding and managing these technologies, leading to potential disruptions in their operations.

Integration with Existing Systems:

Integrating Artificial Intelligence solutions with existing legacy systems can be challenging. Many real estate firms use outdated software and processes that may not be compatible with modern Artificial Intelligence technologies. This can result in significant time and resource investments to ensure seamless integration, which can be a deterrent for many organizations (Williams & Hardy, 2020).

Cultural Resistance:

The adoption of Artificial Intelligence often requires a cultural shift within organizations. Employees and management may be resistant to change, particularly if they are accustomed to traditional methods of operation. Overcoming this resistance involves significant effort in change management, training, and communication to highlight the benefits and alleviate concerns about Artificial Intelligence technologies.

Fear of Uncertainty:

There is often fear and uncertainty associated with new technologies. Real estate professionals may be hesitant to adopt Artificial Intelligence due to a lack of understanding or fear of the unknown. This can result in a slower adoption rate and reluctance to invest in Artificial Intelligence innovations (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019).

2.4.2.3 Readiness and Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in Real Estate Market

Resource Availability:

The readiness to adopt Artificial Intelligence varies across the real estate sector. Larger firms with more substantial financial and technological resources are generally more prepared to invest in Artificial Intelligence technologies. In contrast, smaller firms may lag due to limited budgets and technological infrastructure. The availability of resources significantly influences the ability to implement and leverage Artificial Intelligence effectively.

Training and Skill Development:

Successful Artificial Intelligence adoption requires a workforce that is skilled in using these technologies. Training and education are critical to equip real estate professionals with the necessary knowledge and skills to leverage Artificial Intelligence. Continuous professional development programs can help bridge the skill gap and ensure that employees can effectively use Artificial Intelligence tools and systems (Zhu, 2021).

Cultural and Organizational Shift:

Adopting Artificial Intelligence requires a cultural shift within organizations to embrace innovation and change. This involves fostering a mindset that values technological advancement and is open to experimenting with new tools and methods. Organizational leaders must champion Artificial Intelligence adoption and create an environment that supports innovation. Additionally, establishing supportive regulatory frameworks and industry standards can facilitate the ethical and responsible implementation of Artificial Intelligence technologies.

Regulatory Compliance:

Adopting Artificial Intelligence in real estate requires navigating a complex regulatory landscape. Firms must ensure that their Artificial Intelligence implementations comply with local, national, and international regulations, including data protection laws, anti-discrimination regulations, and industry-specific standards. Compliance with these regulations is essential to avoid legal pitfalls and build trust with clients and stakeholders.

Standardization:

Industry standards play a vital role in facilitating Artificial Intelligence adoption. Standardized protocols and best practices help ensure that Artificial Intelligence systems are implemented ethically, securely, and effectively. Collaborative efforts to establish industry standards can provide a framework for real estate firms to follow, reducing uncertainties and promoting widespread adoption of Artificial Intelligence technologies (Goodman & Flaxman, 2017).

Competitive Advantage:

Firms that adopt Artificial Intelligence technologies can gain a competitive advantage by offering more effective, accurate, and personalized services. As more firms begin to leverage Artificial Intelligence,

there is increased competitive pressure on others to follow suit to remain relevant and competitive in the market. This creates a driving force for Artificial Intelligence adoption across the industry.

Customer Expectations:

As Artificial Intelligence technologies become more prevalent, customer expectations evolve. Clients increasingly expect personalized, data-driven insights and faster, more effective service. Real estate firms that fail to meet these expectations risk losing clients to more technologically advanced competitors. Thus, staying attuned to customer demands can drive Artificial Intelligence adoption (Alkassim & Merhej, 2019).

3.5. Prospects of Artificial Intelligence Adoption for Estate Professionals

Improved Efficiency: Artificial Intelligence technologies offer estate professionals the opportunity to streamline their workflows and improve effectiveness by automating repetitive tasks and optimizing processes. Artificial Intelligence-powered tools such as chatbots, virtual assistants, and predictive analytics platforms can handle routine inquiries, schedule appointments, analyze market trends, and manage property listings, allowing professionals to focus their time and resources on higher-value activities (Adesina, 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020; Gartner, 2020).

Decision Making: Artificial Intelligence provides estate professionals with valuable insights and data-driven recommendations to support more informed decision-making processes. By analyzing vast amounts of real estate data, artificial Intelligence algorithms can identify market trends, predict property values, assess investment opportunities, and optimize pricing strategies, enabling professionals to make strategic decisions that maximize returns and minimize risks (Adesina., 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020; Gartner, 2020).

Client Experiences: Artificial intelligence enables estate professionals to deliver personalized and tailored experiences to their clients. Artificial Intelligence-driven recommendation systems can match buyers and renters with properties that align with their preferences and requirements, while virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies can provide immersive property tours and visualization experiences, enhancing customer satisfaction and engagement (Adesina., 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020; Gartner, 2020).

Marketing and Sales Strategies: Artificial Intelligence-powered marketing and sales tools empower real estate professionals to optimize their marketing efforts and target their audience more effectively. By analyzing customer data and behavior, artificial intelligence algorithms can identify potential leads, personalize marketing messages, optimize advertising campaigns, and track engagement metrics, resulting in higher conversion rates and increased sales opportunities (Adesina., 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020; Gartner, 2020).

Property Valuation and Market Trends Analysis: Artificial Intelligence can revolutionize property valuation and market trends analysis by leveraging advanced algorithms to analyze large datasets and identify patterns and trends. Artificial Intelligence-powered valuation models can provide more accurate and timely property valuations by considering a wide range of factors, including market dynamics, property characteristics, and comparable sales data, leading to more informed investment decisions (Adesina, 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020; Gartner, 2020).

Property Management: Artificial Intelligence technologies can optimize property management processes by automating tasks such as maintenance scheduling, tenant communications, and rent collection. Artificial Intelligence-powered property management platforms can analyze tenant data, predict maintenance needs, and optimize resource allocation, leading to improved tenant satisfaction, reduced

operational costs, and increased property value (Adesina, 2020; Oladunjoye & Ogunsemi, 2020; Gartner, 2020).

3.5.1 Best Practices of Artificial Intelligence in Real Estate Markets Around the World

United States

In the United States, Artificial Intelligence is extensively used to enhance property valuation, market analysis, and customer experience. Companies like Zillow and Redfin use Artificial Intelligence algorithms to provide accurate property valuations through Automated Valuation Models (AVMs). These models analyze vast amounts of data, including historical sales, property features, and market trends, to offer precise property price estimates. Additionally, Artificial intelligence-powered Chatbot's and virtual assistants improve customer interactions by providing instant responses to inquiries, scheduling property viewings, and offering personalized property recommendations (Zillow, 2020). These advancements have streamlined the buying and selling process, making it more proficient and user-friendly.

United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom, Artificial Intelligence is being used to predict property market trends and optimize property management. Companies like Zoopla and Rightmove employ artificial intelligence to analyze market data and predict future property price movements, helping investors make informed decisions. Artificial Intelligence-driven tools also assist property managers by automating routine tasks such as maintenance scheduling, tenant communication, and rent collection. This automation enhances operational effectiveness and reduces the likelihood of human error (Rightmove, 2021). The use of Artificial Intelligence in predictive analytics has provided investors and property managers with valuable insights, enabling more strategic decision-making.

China

China has embraced Artificial Intelligence in its real estate market to improve urban planning and property development. Companies like Fang.com use Artificial Intelligence to analyze demographic data, traffic patterns, and environmental factors to determine the best locations for new developments. Artificial Intelligence also helps in designing smart buildings equipped with IoT (Internet of Things) devices that optimize energy consumption, enhance security, and improve the overall living experience for residents. This data-driven approach to urban planning ensures

That new developments meet the needs of the population and contribute to sustainable urban growth (Fang.com, 2022). The integration of artificial intelligence in urban planning has led to more productive and sustainable development projects.

Australia

In Australia, Artificial Intelligence is being utilized to enhance the real estate marketing and sales process. Real estate platforms like Domain and REA Group employ Artificial intelligence-driven marketing tools to target potential buyers with personalized advertisements based on their browsing history and preferences. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies, powered by Artificial Intelligence, allow prospective buyers to take virtual tours of properties from anywhere in the world. This technology not only attracts international buyers but also speeds up the sales process by providing an immersive and detailed view of properties (Domain, 2021). The use of Artificial Intelligence in marketing and virtual tours has expanded the reach and effectiveness of real estate transactions.

Canada

In Canada, Artificial Intelligence is transforming the mortgage and lending process within the real estate market. Companies like RBC and Scotiabank use artificial intelligence to assess creditworthiness and

streamline mortgage approvals. Artificial Intelligence algorithms analyze a range of financial data to provide more accurate risk assessments and personalized loan offers. This not only speeds up the approval process but also reduces the risk of default by ensuring that loans are granted to borrowers with a suitable financial profile (Scotiabank, 2020). The integration of artificial intelligence in the mortgage process has improved the capability and reliability of lending decisions.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Research method refers to a set of strategies through which data is collected, processed, analyzed, stored and presented to provide answers to research questions generated on a certain study.

According to Okoko (2005), the research method provides scaffolding for the validation, proper interpretation and analysis of data, which carefully guides toward the fulfillment or realization of the goals and objectives of the research.

In other words, the research method is the way and manner in which data or information that is necessary for any research work is collected, analyzed, and collated with previous empirical work, which will assist the researcher to make proper inferences about the research being carried out.

This chapter deals with the elements of the research process, it takes into cognizance the research design, population, sample and sampling technique, research instruments, reliability of the instrument, validity of the instrument, administration of the instrument, scoring of the instrument, and data analysis.

3.2 Research Design

Research design addresses the planning of scientific inquiry or designing a strategy for finding out something (Koothari, 2004). This section addresses the plan, structure, and strategy of examining the potential impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on real estate transactions in Nigeria, using Akure as a case study. The planned outline research scheme on which the work was carried out, the structure indicated, specific outline while the strategy shows how the research was carried out

including the method adopted in data collection and analysis. This study would adopt a survey research design to enhance collecting data.

3.3 Target Population

A population is made up of all imaginable components and is the topic of observations about a specific phenomenon that the researcher is interested in (Asika, 2000). Population was defined by Mugenda (2003) as the total collection of people, things, or events that share a particular definition. In other words, the entirety of people who share specific characteristics, are of the utmost interest to the researcher, and satisfy the sample for inclusion in a study. In a survey, there must be a target population that symbolizes the things that provide the necessary data information. The target population for this research comprises the registered real estate professionals in Akure metropolis, duly registered with the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers (NIESV). The estate professionals will be used in this study because they deal in the management and acquisition of properties by Decree 24 of 1975. This managerial function makes them to interact with tenants when serving as agents on rented premises and also property acquisition in the state

3.4 Sample Frame

The sampling frame is the list of elements from which a population sample is selected (Kothari 2004). The sampling frame for estate professionals which includes property valuers, estate agents, and developers in Akure metropolis was derived from the 2024 Nigeria Directory. The 2024 Directory of the Estate Professionals in Akure metropolis shows that there are twenty-eight (28) registered members of the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers is sixteen (16) registered Estate Surveying and Valuation firms in Akure metropolis (NIESV directory, 2024).

3.5 Sample Size

According to Kumar (2011), a sample size is a list of respondents drawn from the entire population from which the necessary data is acquired. The number of observations picked from the universe to comprise a statistical sample, according to Kothari and Garg (2014), is referred to as the sample size. The impracticability of sampling every member of the large population of study informs the adoption of a manageable number as sample size for data collection. According to the entire twenty-eight (28) registered members of the Nigerian Institution of Estate Surveyors and Valuers in the Akure metropolis will serve as the sample size. This is important since Israel (2002) stated that it is appropriate to employ the full population (census) when it is small (200 or fewer).

3.6 Sampling Techniques

The population to be used in a universe population is determined by researchers using a sampling technique. According to Kumar (2011), an exact sketch must be decided upon before any kind of data gathering to obtain a sample from a specific universe. Any attempt to gather data from every estate professional in the research region may be technically and financially complex, as well as time-

consuming. Oke (2015) backed this up by asserting that it would be illogical, expensive, and practically challenging to collect data from the full population in many research areas. As a result, it is critical to think of a sound sampling strategy for the sample. Sampling techniques are divided into two categories: probability and non-probability. Each member of the population has a known non-zero probability of being chosen in the probability sampling technique. In a non-random manner, members of the population are chosen for the non-probability sampling procedure. These include snowball sampling, quota sampling, purposeful sampling, and convenience sampling. Convenience sampling techniques will be used for this investigation. Mishra and Alok (2017) noted that convenience sampling is an approach used to choose populations that are easily accessible

3.6 Data Type and Source

Olusegun (2003) defined data as the collection of facts, numbers, and abstract items from which information is derived. In essence, there are two categories of data. These data are both primary and secondary. Primary sources of data will be used to gather the pertinent data needed for this study.

3.7.1 Primary Source

The primary source of data collection in this study will be the questionnaire method. The questionnaire method will be used as the main source of data collection in this study. A questionnaire is a collection of questions used to gather data in connection to the variables mentioned in the study's objective. In this research, a questionnaire will be administered to all the estate professionals in the Akure metropolis.

3.8 Data Collection and Instruments

These are the practical methods for gathering information from the numerous sources that are available on the subject of interest in the field. Kothari and Garg (2014) suggest that the researcher should develop a set of questions to elicit particular data about a given issue. The thoughtfully created survey included a multiple-choice layout with numerous tables and checkboxes. The opening component of the questionnaire was used to compile general background information about the respondents (such as personality qualities, role in the office, educational background, and years of experience). The questions in the questionnaires created for this project would be constructed in such a way as to elicit significant responses, which are anticipated to aid in the analysis of the current situation. This will be carried out to evaluate the caliber of the field data gathered before beginning a statistical analysis, in other sections like B, C, D, E, and F, the respondent will be requested to state their view by checking the appropriate box to collect relevant data. Each of the questionnaire's questions will be designed to evaluate a certain facet of the stated goals. Through the firm visit and an online survey delivered to email addresses, the questions will be self-administered to estate professionals in the Akure metropolis.

3.9 Method of data analysis.

In the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data, data collected is analyzed based on the objectives of the study.

Serial	Objectives	Type of Data Needed	Method of Data Collection	Method of Data Analysis
1.	Examine the perceptions of ESV towards Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market.	Qualitative data	Questionnaires	Descriptive Analysis
2.	Assess the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area.	Quantitative data	Questionnaires	Descriptive Analysis
3.	Identify the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area.	Quantitative data	Questionnaires	Linear Regression
4.	Examine the suitable intelligence technology for addressing real estate challenges in the study area	Quantitative data	Questionnaires	Relativity Important Index

3.10 Data analysis and present action

This refers to the different instruments used for the analysis and presentation of the raw data obtained during the field survey (Okoro, 2000). The data collected will be analyzed using descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequencies, and averages. The numeric expression will also be used to determine the relationship between variables

Chapter Four

4.1 Introduction

This chapter mainly presents and analyzes the data collected from field surveys through questionnaire administration in the study area. The results of the data presented will assist in having a cleaner picture of various circumstances in the study area. It is pertinent at this stage to once again reinstate the fact that the essence of this study and survey is to help collect relevant data that will be of utmost importance towards achieving the research aim.

This chapter is divided into five sections, the first section provides an overview of data gathered and the distribution of respondents; the second section examines the data retrieved to understand how familiar are the respondents to Artificial Intelligence and explores the perceptions of estate surveyors and valuer towards artificial intelligence in Akure property market. The third section assesses the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area; the fourth section identifies the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area; and lastly, the fifth section examines the suitable Artificial Intelligence technology for addressing Real Estate challenges in the study area.

4.2 Questionnaire Administration

Table 1: Questionnaire distribution and retrieval

S/N	QUESTIONNAIRES	
1	Questionnaires Administered	28
2	Questionnaires Received	24
3	Questionnaires Not Received	4
4	Response Rate (%)	85.71%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 showed that out of 28 questionnaires administered to the respondent which are the registered Estate Surveyor and Valuers in Akure metropolis, 24 questionnaires were retrieved, 24 questionnaires were returned for analysis translating to 85.71% of the retrieval rate. This was possible due to the technique used that is google forms and physical administering the questionnaire on the spot and waiting to retrieve them immediately; the respondents were thorough with answering the questionnaires. Babbie (2007) also suggested that any return rate that is over 50% can be reported, over 60% response rate is good, and that over 70% is excellent. This implied that the questionnaires retrieved from the surveyed respondents is statistically adequate to represent the whole form inference can be made for this study; hence the results of the finds can be relied on.

4.3 Background Information of the Respondents

Table 2: Background Information of the Respondents

Items		Frequency	Per Cent
Age Range	Below 20 Years	1	4.2
	21 – 30 Years	13	54.2
	31 – 40 Years	7	29.2
	41 – 50 Years	2	8.3
	50 Years Above	1	4.2
Total		24	100.0
Gender	Male	19	79.2
	Female	5	20.8
Total		24	100.0
Education	Bachelor’s Degree	13	54.2
	Master’s Degree	7	29.2
	Professional Certification	4	16.7
Total		24	100.0

Years of Experience	0 – 5 Years	12	50.0
	6 -10 Years	6	25.0
	11 -15 Years	6	25.0
Total		24	100.0
Responses	Yes	23	95.8
	No	1	4.2
Total		24	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in Table 2 shows the breakdown of data collected according to a questionnaire retrieved with information from relevant estate surveyors and valuers in the Akure property market.

The age distribution of respondents reveals that 4.2% are below 20 years, while the majority, at 54.2%, fall within the 21-30 years range. The 31-40 years age group comprises 29.2% of respondents, followed by 8.3% in the 41-50 years category, and another 4.2% are above 50 years. The gender indicates a predominance of males, with 79.2%, while females is 20.8%. The educational qualifications, 54.2% hold a Bachelor's degree, 29.2% have a Master's degree, and 16.7% possess a professional certification. The total number of respondents remains 24. The respondents' experience in the industry shows that 50% have between 0 to 5 years of experience, while 25% have between 6 to 10 years, and another 25% decrease within the 11 to 15 years category. The total number of respondents is 24. The respondents shows that 23 out of the 24 have a knowledge of Artificial Intelligence; which is 95.8%, while only 1 respondent didn't have a prior knowledge of Artificial Intelligence; which is 4.2%.

4.4 To examine the perceptions of ESV toward Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure study market

Table 3: Perceptions toward Artificial Intelligence

AI Technology	Rank	Mean	Std. Deviation
Automated Valuation Model	1	0.270	0.618
Virtual Assistants/Chatbots	2	0.292	0.582
Predictive Analytics	3	0.348	0.815
Property Management Systems	4	0.353	0.844
Virtual Reality	5	0.401	0.800
Augmented Reality	6	0.506	1.008

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 shows the descriptive data analysis of the perception of Artificial Intelligence technology in the Akure property market. The first ranking is Automated Valuation Model with a mean value of 0.270 followed by Virtual Assistants/Chatbots with a mean value of 0.292. Property management systems came third with a mean of 0.353, Predictive Analytics with a mean value of 0.348; Virtual Reality with a mean value of 0.401 and the sixth is Augmented Reality with a mean value of 0.506. The variables are ranked in descending order based on their mean values. The top three variables are Automated Valuation Model, Virtual Assistants/Chatbots, and Property Management Systems, which have mean value of 0.270, 0.292, and 0.353 respectively. This suggests that these variables may be the main perceptives of ESV in the study area. However, it is important to note that without conducting further statistical analysis, such as regression analysis, it is difficult to draw any firm conclusions about the relationship between these variables.

4.5 To assess the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area

In order to assess the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in Akure metropolis, the analytical method used is descriptive statistics. This is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Mean Score of factors influencing the implementation

Influencing AI Implementation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	Rank
Government Policies and Regulations	1.23	0.508	2.387	7.144	1
Training and Skill Development	1.28	0.634	3.291	17.770	2
Technological Readiness	1.35	0.508	0.754	-1.956	3
Market Demand	1.51	0.864	2.776	13.859	4
Organizational Support	1.55	0.819	1.176	-0.062	5
Financial Investment	1.63	0.942	1.245	0.466	6
Regulatory Compliance	2.05	1.005	-0.125	-2.454	7

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 provide insights into the factors influencing Artificial Intelligence implementation, ranked by importance based on their mean scores. Government policies and regulations rank as the most significant factor (mean = 1.23, std. deviation = 0.508), with a high positive skewness (2.387) and a sharply peaked distribution (kurtosis = 7.144), indicating that most respondents view it as highly influential. Training and skill development follow closely (mean = 1.28), with an even higher skewness (3.291) and extreme kurtosis (17.770), suggesting that a large number of respondents consider this crucial, though a few may not. Technological readiness ranks third (mean = 1.35), showing less skewness (0.754) and a negative kurtosis (-1.956), implying more balanced responses. Market demand (mean = 1.51) is also a key factor but with high skewness (2.776) and kurtosis (13.859), reflecting a strong consensus on its influence. Organizational support (mean = 1.55) and financial investment (mean = 1.63) rank fifth and sixth, sequentially, with moderate skewness and lower kurtosis, indicating varied responses. Regulatory

compliance (mean = 2.05) is the least influential, with near-zero skewness (-0.125) and negative kurtosis (-2.454), suggesting a more evenly spread perception of its relevance.

Figure 1: Shows a mean score and standard deviation of the factors influencing Artificial Intelligence

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 1 represents a Bar chart that shows the factors influencing Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market, based on mean scores and ranked in order of importance. The error bars indicate the standard deviation for each factor, reflecting the variation in responses. Government policies and regulations rank as the most significant factor, while regulatory compliance ranks the lowest.

4.6 To identify the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area.

To assess the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area, the analytical method used is Linear Regression.

Table 5: Model Summary of the barriers to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence

Barrier	Mean	Std Deviation	Pearson Correlation	Significance (1-tailed)
Integration with Existing Systems	1.26	0.576	0.400	0.148
High Costs of Implementation	1.35	0.611	0.738	0.013
Data Privacy and Security	1.46	0.715	-0.017	0.483
Complexity of the Technology	1.46	0.715	0.695	0.021
Fear of Uncertainty	1.60	0.848	0.052	0.052
Job Displacement	2.12	1.304	0.966	0.000
Cultural Resistance	2.17	1.252	0.031	0.014

The dependent variable; Responses got from the knowledge of Artificial Intelligence

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 5 shows the barriers to implementing Artificial Intelligence in the study area, with data analyzed using linear regression. Job displacement (mean = 2.12, Pearson correlation = 0.966, $p = 0.000$) is a significant barrier, with a strong positive correlation, indicating that concerns over job loss greatly impact AI adoption. Cultural resistance (mean = 2.17, Pearson correlation = 0.031, $p = 0.014$) also shows statistical significance, although the correlation is weak. High costs of implementation (mean = 1.35, Pearson correlation = 0.738, $p = 0.013$) and complexity of the technology (mean = 1.46, Pearson correlation = 0.695, $p = 0.021$) are the main barriers, both with strong positive correlations and statistical significance, suggesting these are challenges. Also, integration with existing systems (mean = 1.26) has a moderate correlation (0.400) but is not statistically significant ($p = 0.148$). Data privacy and security (mean = 1.46) and fear of uncertainty (mean = 1.60) have weak correlations and lack statistical significance.

Figure 2: Bar Chart showing the Barriers to Artificial Intelligence implementation in the study area

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 2 shows a Bar graph that represents the mean scores for each barrier, while the line plot shows the Pearson correlation values. The statistical significance (p-values) of each factor is labeled above the bars, highlighting which barriers are the most critical based on the data

4.7 Examine the suitable Artificial Intelligence technology for addressing real estate challenges in the study area.

To examine the suitable Artificial Intelligence technology for addressing real estate challenges, The Relative Importance Index (RII) analysis method is used. This method is used for ranking and evaluate

different Artificial Intelligence technologies to determine which one is most suitable for addressing the challenges in the real estate market.

Table 6: Model Summary of the Importance of Artificial Intelligence Tools

Artificial Intelligence Tools	Relative Importance Index	Rank
Maintenance Automation	0.4000	1
Data Extraction	0.4000	1
Automated Valuation	0.3917	3
Immersive Property Tours	0.3417	4
Market Forecasting	0.2833	5
Document Processing	0.2500	6
Secure Transactions	0.2417	7
Clients Interaction	0.2417	7
Marketing Tools	0.2333	9

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 6 shows that Maintenance Automation and Data Extraction are the most suitable Artificial Intelligence technologies for addressing real estate challenges in the study area, both ranked first with a Relative Importance Index (RII) of 0.4000. Automated Valuation follows closely, ranked third with 0.3917, making it another key tool. Immersive Property Tours (RII = 0.3417) ranks fourth, showing its growing importance for enhancing buyer experiences. Technologies like Market Forecasting (0.2833) and Document Processing (0.2500) rank lower, while Secure Transactions and Client Interaction share the seventh spot (both 0.2417), with Marketing Tools being the least rated (0.2333).

Figure 3: Bar Chart showing the ranked importance of Artificial Intelligence

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 3 shows a Bar Chart showing the Relative Importance Index (RII) for each Artificial Intelligence tool, with ranks labeled at the top of each bar. Maintenance Automation and Data Extraction are ranked highest, indicating their significance in the real estate market.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATION, AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

Chapter four presents and analyzes the data collected from the field surveys. In conclusion and recommendation. This chapter presents the summary of the analysis based on the research objective.

Which are to:

- i. Examine the perceptions of ESV towards Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market.
- ii. Assess the factors influencing the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the study area.
- iii. Identify the barriers to implementing Artificial Intelligence in the study area.
- iv. Examine the suitable Artificial Intelligence technology for addressing real estate challenges in the study area.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

Objective One: The findings reveal that the majority of estate surveyors and valuers (ESV) in the Akure property market have a positive perception of Artificial Intelligence. A significant 95.8% of respondents indicated familiarity with Artificial Intelligence technologies, demonstrating an awareness of its potential applications in real estate. Among the various Artificial Intelligence tools, Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) ranked highest, followed by Virtual Assistants and Property Management Systems. This indicates that professionals in the field recognize Artificial Intelligence's value in improving property valuation accuracy and operational efficiency. However, more advanced technologies such as Virtual

Reality and Augmented Reality received lower perception scores, suggesting that their adoption is still in its infancy within the Akure property market.

Objective Two: The study identified several key factors influencing Artificial Intelligence implementation in Akure's real estate market. Government policies and regulations ranked as the most important factor, indicating that supportive policies could encourage Artificial Intelligence adoption, while restrictive ones could hinder it. Training and skill development also emerged as the main, highlighting the need for professionals to acquire the necessary expertise to effectively use Artificial Intelligence tools. Technological readiness, including infrastructure and market demand, further plays a role in determining the pace of Artificial Intelligence adoption. Organizational support and financial investment, though important, were ranked lower, indicating varied responses on their impact on Artificial Intelligence implementation. Overall, the readiness of the market to embrace Artificial Intelligence largely depends on policy support, skills training, and available technology infrastructure.

Objective Three: The study found that the most significant barrier to Artificial Intelligence implementation in the Akure property market is job displacement, with respondents expressing concerns that Artificial Intelligence might replace human roles in real estate processes. Cultural resistance, driven by fear of technology, was also identified as a challenge, though its impact was statistically less significant. High implementation costs and the complexity of integrating Artificial Intelligence technologies with existing systems were other major barriers, highlighting the financial and technical constraints smaller real estate firms may face. Interestingly, data privacy and security, often cited as key challenges in Artificial Intelligence adoption, were not seen as a major obstacle in this particular market.

Objective Four: In terms of Artificial Intelligence tools suitable for addressing real estate challenges in Akure, Maintenance Automation and Data Extraction technologies ranked highest. These tools are viewed as essential for improving operational efficiency and streamlining data management in the real

estate sector. Automated Valuation models, already perceived favourably by ESVs, also ranked highly as a suitable tool. On the other hand, tools like Market Forecasting, Document Processing, and Marketing Tools were ranked lower, indicating that while these technologies have potential, they are not yet seen as notable for addressing the immediate challenges faced in the Akure property market.

5.3 Recommendation

1. It is recommended that continuous education and awareness campaigns be conducted to further improve the perception of Artificial Intelligence among estate surveyors and valuers. While the majority of respondents are familiar with Artificial Intelligence, there is a need to provide in-depth training on more advanced Artificial Intelligence technologies, such as Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality, which have yet to gain substantial traction. By demonstrating the value of these tools in enhancing client experiences and decision-making processes, more professionals in the real estate sector can be encouraged to adopt Artificial Intelligence solutions.
2. To enhance the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the Akure property market, the government should create supportive policies and regulatory frameworks that promote the adoption of Artificial Intelligence technologies while safeguarding ethical concerns, such as data privacy and security. In addition, educational institutions and professional bodies must collaborate in providing specialized training programs that equip real estate professionals with the skills needed to utilize Artificial Intelligence tools. Strengthening technological infrastructure, such as improving internet connectivity and access to Artificial Intelligence software, will also accelerate the integration of Artificial Intelligence in the industry.
3. To address the barriers to Artificial Intelligence implementation, particularly concerns over job displacement, it is recommended that stakeholders focus on promoting Artificial Intelligence as a complementary tool that enhances productivity rather than replaces human roles. Also, providing

financial incentives, such as grants or loans for smaller real estate firms, can alleviate the high costs associated with Artificial Intelligence implementation. And, simplifying Artificial Intelligence systems and providing user-friendly interfaces will help overcome the complexity of technology adoption. Lastly, fostering a culture of innovation and change within organizations will reduce cultural resistance to Artificial Intelligence integration.

4. Given the findings, it is recommended that real estate firms prioritize the adoption of Maintenance Automation and Data Extraction technologies to address immediate operational challenges. These tools should be integrated into daily business operations to streamline processes, improve accuracy, and reduce costs. Additionally, Automated Valuation Models should be widely implemented to enhance the accuracy of property assessments. As market readiness increases, firms can gradually invest in other Artificial Intelligence tools, such as Market Forecasting and Immersive Property Tours, to further improve their competitive edge and customer engagement.

5.4 Conclusion

The research demonstrated that estate surveyors and valuers (ESVs) in Akure have a generally positive perception of Artificial Intelligence, particularly in areas like Automated Valuation Models and Property Management Systems. This indicates a readiness among real estate professionals to adopt Artificial Intelligence for improving transactional accuracy and operational efficiency. However, there is still a need for greater awareness and training on more advanced Artificial Intelligence technologies, such as Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality, which have the potential to further streamline real estate processes. Key factors influencing Artificial Intelligence adoption in Akure include government policies, training, technological infrastructure, and market demand. Supportive regulations and improved training programs are essential to overcoming challenges and facilitating wider Artificial Intelligence adoption.

The barriers identified such as job displacement fears, high costs, and cultural resistance, can be mitigated through strategic interventions, including promoting Artificial Intelligence as a tool for enhancing productivity, providing financial support to smaller firms, and fostering a culture of innovation. In terms of Artificial Intelligence tools suitable for addressing real estate challenges, technologies like Maintenance Automation and Data Extraction emerged as highly relevant for improving transaction efficiency, reducing manual labor, and enhancing data management processes. Automated Valuation Models were also identified as important in providing more accurate property assessments, ultimately speeding up transactions and improving market transparency. Achieving the research aim of leveraging Artificial Intelligence to improve real estate transactions in Akure, and potentially in Nigeria as a whole, is feasible with targeted efforts. By focusing on training, infrastructure development, supportive policies, and overcoming cultural and financial barriers, the Nigerian real estate market can unlock the full potential of Artificial Intelligence, leading to enhanced business efficiency, transparency, and growth in the property market.

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